

Evaluating Pro-Poor Tourism as a Panacea for Rural Infrastructural Development in Cross River State, Nigeria

Felix Onen Eteng & Eja Iwara Eja
University of Calabar, Calaba-Nigeria

Abstract

This research examined the pro-poor tourism as a panacea for rural infrastructural development in Cross River State. Two local government areas such as Calabar Municipality and Yakurr Local Government Areas were used. One community was selected from each Local Government were for this study. Questionnaire was used in data collection and information such as types of tourism activities economic benefits of tourism activities. The questionnaires were used to operationalise the concept of pro-poor tourism with respect to rural welfare sustenance and infrastructural development in the area. Two hypotheses were stated and tested. The first hypothesis investigates if there exists a relationship between activities and the types of rural development generated by tourism activities in the area. The second hypothesis tries to investigate if there exists a relationship between tourism activities and the economic benefits that tourism activities generated in the communities. The research findings indicate that tourism activities in the area have significantly operationalised the concept of pro-poor tourism in the two local government areas with specific reference to the occurred economic benefits and the various developments brought by tourism activities in the area. The results were further explained in the tested hypotheses which indicate a strong relationship between tourism activities and types of development and economic benefits brought by tourism activities in the area. However, the results from the tested hypotheses and other findings show that in spite the operationalisation of pro-poor tourism using tourism activities. Tourism activities are not devoid of challenges in the area. Therefore, all stakeholders in the tourism industry must provide a mechanism that would ensure the sustainability of the tourism activities in the area.

Keywords: Pro-poor tourism, Infrastructural Development, Cross River State.

Résumé

Cette recherche a examiné le tourisme en faveur des pauvres comme une panacée pour le développement des infrastructures rurales dans l'État de Cross River. Deux municipalités telles que la municipalité de Calabar et celle de Yakurr ont été utilisées et une communauté sélectionnée dans chaque municipalité a été sélectionnée pour cette étude. Un questionnaire a été utilisé dans la collecte de données et des informations telles que les types d'activités touristiques, les avantages économiques des activités touristiques ont été utilisés pour opérationnaliser le concept de tourisme favorable aux pauvres en matière de bien-être rural et de développement des infrastructures dans la région. Deux hypothèses ont été énoncées et testées. La première hypothèse étudie s'il existe une relation entre les activités et les types de développement rural générés par les activités touristiques dans la région. La seconde hypothèse tente d'étudier s'il existe une relation entre les activités touristiques et les avantages économiques que les activités touristiques génèrent dans les communautés

touristiques. Les résultats de la recherche indiquent que les activités touristiques dans la région ont significativement opérationnalisé le concept de tourisme en faveur des pauvres dans les deux municipalités avec une référence spécifique aux avantages économiques et aux divers développements apportés par les activités touristiques dans la région. Les résultats ont été davantage expliqués dans les hypothèses testées qui indiquent une forte relation entre les activités touristiques et les types de développement et les avantages économiques apportés par les activités touristiques dans la région. Cependant, les résultats des hypothèses testées et d'autres résultats montrent qu'en dépit de l'opérationnalisation du tourisme en faveur des pauvres utilisant les activités touristiques, la présence d'activités touristiques n'est pas dépourvue de défis dans la région. Par conséquent, tous les intervenants dans les industries touristiques doivent fournir un mécanisme qui assurerait la durabilité des activités touristiques dans la région

Mots-clés : Tourisme en faveur des pauvres, Développement des infrastructures, Etat de Cross River

Introduction

The pro-poor tourism and infrastructural development is targeted towards providing an enabling environment that would enhance tourism development in a destination. Contextual variables like governance, leadership and budget from one generation to another have been directed towards non- pro-poor tourism culture (politics, bureaucracy, sport and football). Motivational resources like research which can trigger infrastructural development was neglected as government research institutions, agencies or the universities lack funds which serve as driving factors for technological development and assistance in order to establish these facilities for sustainable pro-poor tourism development in the area.

However, pro-poor tourism and infrastructural development has been the concern of scholars, public and private stakeholders in Cross River State. This increasing concern is predicated upon the expectations that pro-poor tourism and infrastructural development will result in rural transformation, increase in revenue to the State, rural dwellers and pro-poor tourism promoters. Besides, the system will likely generate employment to the teeming rural population and ensure improvement in the living standard of the people who for years have been yearning for progress. As part of the gains of pro-poor tourism, rural socio-economic development in terms of health facilities, roads, communication network, mass transit and service delivery will be given impetus in the planning of the area. This will attract tourists to the State.

Regrettably, these expectations have been a mirage as pro-poor tourism and infrastructural development have been seriously marred in the area by poor governance and leadership failure in public sector management. Consequently, there have been noticeable features of poor rural transportation system and service delivery, poor rural accommodation that cannot be measured by any international standard, lack of potable water supply, poor communication network coverage, and series of security challenges that usually arise from communal clashes or intertribal wars. These challenges posed by the rural environment constitute a problem which usually scare tourists and completely drive them away from their tourism destinations. This is because tourists are human beings and nobody wants to die in a strange land because of sightseeing and entertainment (Eteng & Eja, 2017). Therefore,

following the imperatives of pro-poor tourism and infrastructural development in Cross River State, this study will examine the place of tourism activities as a component for operationalizing pro-poor tourism for rural infrastructural development and livelihood sustenance with respect to investigating the challenges and prospects of pro-poor tourism.

Literature review

The place of infrastructural development in pro-poor tourism

Pro-poor tourism is a specialized field of study which is rapidly growing with the need for strong infrastructural base for service delivery and necessary future expansion. As usually expected, the process would involve the establishment of facilities, amenities or equipment that are capable of boosting tourism through public/private sector investment in auxillary services which are necessary support for the tourism industry. The ancillary support will make pro-poor tourism attractive and promote the quality of life of the people to become better than before due to business and employment opportunities. Infrastructure based development is globally a driving force for sustainable pro-poor tourism. One of the infrastructure is the provision of housing to cater for the accommodation of the tourists in far away destination from their homes. Therefore, accommodation which must be of international standard is an integral unit that must be met to attract tourist attention. To accelerate the expected progression rate, there is need for public/private investment in hotels or buildings at affordable prices to the tourists. Unfortunately, the government involvement and budgetary allocation for this facility has been retrogressive due to inadequacy of funds and bad governance. Studies show that investment in hotels and interest in providing accommodation for tourists is private sector driven. The private sector is also dominant in travel agency business (Eja & Otu, 2015).

Pro-poor tourism infrastructural development provides the ground to stand for successful and attractive tourism potentials. This is commonly practiced in destinations like Brazil, Kenya, Uganda, South Africa, etc. Therefore for better tourism development potentials, pro-poor tourism will require the provisions of "health centres, maternity homes, renovation of houses, provision of amusement parks, marine resort, portable water, water fountains, libraries, recreational centres, widening of existing play grounds" (Eteng & Anam, 2016). The process also involves providing electricity, street lights, decorating of waterfalls, lakes, museums, and village play grounds and hotels to look attractive. There is need to improve the rural communication system and widen the network coverage of the various Mobile Telecommunication Networks. The use of internet service providers and facilities as an indispensable tool for pro-poor tourism development will make the difference. This will give impetus to pro-poor tourism development and draw tourist to these destinations.

The provision of rural mass transit system facilitates service delivery. Most rural areas are inaccessible due to poor terrain or bad roads especially during the wet season. In some cases, movement is hindered due to water, forest and mountains. The use of mechanically propelled boats, tricycle vehicle (Keke Napep) are necessary imperatives that can support and facilitate pro-poor tourism centres.

The provision of shopping centres, eatries, and other confectionaries promote business tourism which in turn attract entertainment facilities thereby providing the

"enabling environment for investment" (Eja & Otu, 2015). The provision of outdoor games facilities, equipment for sports or gymnastics, availability of conference centres, banking system, laundry services make pro-poor tourism development a reality. Infrastructural development in all political and administrative systems requires harnessing the resource potentials of the state. This will usher in an experience that will accelerate progress in the provision of the needed facilities to attract tourists. Regrettably, the policy of the various regimes towards infrastructural development has been one of neglect. This lamentable situation has been due to lack of co-ordination, harmonisation and control.

The pro-poor tourism concept

Advocates of pro-poor tourism (Goodwin & Ashley, 2001) argue that tourism has a number of advantages compared to other economic sectors in terms of its potential to generate pro-poor growth in particular, due to its size, labour intensity, and potential for cross sectoral linkages and potential in countries with few other competitive exports. Conversely that tourism driven by foreign private sector interests is not an activity suited for poverty elimination, because economic benefits are not maximised due to high level of foreign ownership high leakages and few linkages (Ashley & Roe, 2002). This means that tourism imposes substantial non-economic costs on the poor—displacement, loss of access to resources as well as cultural and social disruption. Proponents of pro-poor tourism however, note the characteristics of tourism which seem particularly strong to warrant it fit for poverty alleviation as including the following:

- i. Tourism is consumed at the point of production. Ashley, Roe and Goodwin (2001) note that tourism delivers consumers to the product rather than the other goods and services which enhance potential links for other enterprises and products.
- ii. Most export industries depend on financial, productive and human capital. Tourism depends on these but also on natural capital for example wildlife and culture, which are assets that some poor have or are gaining increasing control over, especially in cases where decentralization and devolution of tenure are occurring (Mowforth, 1998)
- iii. Tourism is often reported to be more labour intensive than productive sectors and can provide the much sought for employment in poor communities.
- iv. There is a greater uptake of jobs by women than in other sectors although it is unknown if more jobs are taken by the poor and unskilled (Page & Getz, 1997)

Against this background, it is clear that tourism has more potential of becoming a pro-poor tourism initiative than other options especially those based on agriculture. However, the pro-poor tourism concept emphasize tourism in a given destination that takes care of the poor people, therefore, the Calabar festival celebration as a form of tourism activities would enhance the socio-economic livelihood of the people in Calabar Municipality as a tourism destination.

Methodology

This research was conducted in Cross River State and two Local Government Areas were used which including Calabar Municipality and Yakurr Local Government Areas. In order to carry out the research one community was selected in each Local Government Area, Ikot Ansa in Calabar Municipality and Ugep in Yakurr LGA. These Local

Governments were selected due to the fact that they constitute the major centre for tourism activities in the State. Forty household heads were drawn from the rural communities in which two hundred household heads were drawn from each community. The purposive sampling technique was used to select the household heads based on the types of information needed for this research. The four hundred household heads constitute the sample size for this study. However, rationale for using two hundred household heads across board was to allow for equal representation. The questionnaires were administered to the various household heads with the aid of field assistants from the two rural communities. The likertscale of 1 to 5 was used to show the level of strength, weaknesses and which of the tourism activities that flounce greatly economic development in the two local government areas. Two hypotheses were stated which include there is no significant relationship between tourism activities and the types of development generated by tourism activities in these rural areas. The second hypothesis was to investigate if there was or not a significant relationship between tourism activities and the socio-economic benefits generated by tourism activities in the rural communities. The two hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation which tries to investigate the relationship between two variables X and Y variable.

Empirical operation and analysis of pro-poor tourism

Tourism activities in the Area

The types of tourism activities in the study represented in table 1 indicate that festivals and traditional dances were the major tourism activities in the area with values of 24.25 percent and 11.25 percent. It was discovered in table 1 that other tourism activities such as traditional wrestling and sports competition were also tourism activities that propel rural development in the area with values of 9.75 percent and 7.75 percent even though all the above mentioned variables indicating tourism activities were present in the area with value of 40.5 percent.

Table 1: Various Types of tourism activities that create livelihood sustenance in the areas

Tourism activities	Calabar Municipality (Ikot Ansa)	Yakurr LGA (Ugep)	Total (X)	Percentage
Wrestling	22	17	39	9.75
Traditional dances	21	24	45	11.25
Festivals	46	51	97	24.25
Sports competition	20	11	31	7.75
Others	11	15	26	6.5
All of the above	80	82	163	40.5
Total	200	200	400	100

Source: Field survey (2018)

Development brought by tourism activities

The development brought by tourism activities presented in table 2 shows that tourism activities have brought various types of development in the two communities. These developments include enhancement of communication network, increase in business activities increase in road construction, provision of electricity and provision of pipe-borne water. It was noticed that increase in business activities and enhancement of communication network were the major developments brought by tourism activities in the area as noticed in table 2 with values of 29.5 percent and 11.25 percent followed by provision of pipe-borne water with a value of 8.75 percent. Table 2 indicates that increase in road construction and provision of electricity were also developments brought by tourism activities with values 8.5 percent and 5.5 percent.

Table 2: Development brought by tourism activities

Development	Calabar municipality (Ikot Ansa)	Yakurr LGA (Ugep)	Total (Y)	Percentage
Enhanced communication network	21	24	445	11.25
Increase in business activities	60	58	118	29.5
Increase in road construction	16	18	34	8.5
Provision of electricity	12	10	22	5.5
Provision of pipe-borne water	15	20	35	8.75
All of the above	26	70	146	36.5
Total	200	200	400	100

Source: Field survey (2018)

Economic benefits from tourism activities

The economic benefits from tourism activities as presented in table 3 show that tourism activities in the area have given rise to various economic benefits to the two rural communities such as employment opportunities, increase in income generation, emerging business increase in government revenue among others. Table 3 indicates that emergence of business and increase in income generation were the major economic benefits brought by tourism activities with values of 24.25 percent and 11.5 percent followed by 10.24 percent. It was noticed in table 3 that increase in government revenue and increase in investment were also economic benefits from tourism activities in the area with values of 10 percent and 8.75 percent.

Table 3: Economic benefits from tourism activities

Economic benefits	Calabar municipality (Ikot Ansa)	Yakurr LGA (Ugep)	Total (Y)	Percentage
Employment opportunities	23	18	41	10.25
Increase in income generation	22	24	46	11,5
Increase investment	18	17	35	8.75
Increase in government revenue	11	28	40	10
Emergence of businesses	51	46	97	24.25
All of the above	75	66	141	35.25
Total	200	200	400	100

Source: Field survey (2018)

The result of hypothesis 1 which tries to investigate whether or not there exists relationship between tourism activities and the types of development generated from tourism activities in the study area as presented in table 4. The result from the analysis revealed that a strong relationship exists between tourism activities and types of development with a calculated value of 0.65 and a tabulated value of 0.165. This result indicates that tourism activities in the study area have significantly enhanced the development of the two communities under investigation.

Table 4: Summary result of hypothesis 1

		Tourism activities	Type of development
Tourism activities	Pearson		
	Correlation	1	.647
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.165
	N	6	6
Type of development	Pearson		
	Correlation	.647	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.165	
	N	6	6

Tourism activities that greatly influence economic development

Tourism activities that greatly influence economic development in the two rural communities presented in table 5 indicate that traditional festivals were the major tourism activities that greatly influence economic development in the two rural communities with

values of 38.5 percent and 35.5 percent, Ikot Ansa and Ugep with values of 20.5 percent and 22 percent. It was also noticed in the data presented in table 5 that sports competitions in Ugep in Yakurr Local Government area have great influence on rural development with a value of 22 percent in the Area as compared to sports competitions in Ikot Ansa with a low value of 18 percent.

Table 5: Tourism activities greatly influence economic growth and development in the study areas

Tourism activities	Calabar municipality (Ikot Ansa)				Total	Percentage
	Agree	Strongly agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree		
Wrestling	23	11	4	6	44	22
Traditional dance	15	14	6	8	43	21.5
Festivals	36	38	2	1	77	38.5
Sports competition	11	10	8	7	36	18
Total	85	73	20	22	200	100
Tourism activities	Yakurr LGA (Ugep)				Total	Percentage
	Agree	Strongly agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree		
Wrestling	19	13	3	6	41	20.5
Traditional dance	24	15	3	2	44	22
Festivals	31	37	2	1	71	35.5
Sports competition	18	5	12	9	44	22
Total	92	70	20	18	200	100

Source: Field survey (2018)

The result of hypothesis 2 presented in table 6 indicates if or not there exists a relationship between tourism activities and socio-economic benefits. The summary result of hypothesis 2 shows that a strong connection exists between tourism activities and socio-economic development of the rural area as observed with a high calculated value of 0.62 and a tabulated value of 0.28 showing that the existence of tourism activities has significantly impacted on the wellbeing of the people in the two communities.

The Pearson correlation was carried out to show the strength of the linear association between variables. The Pearson correlation ranges between -1 percent negative correlations to 1 percent positive correlation. According to Cohen (1992) guidelines for the interpretation of correlation coefficient, a weak correlation values ranges from -0.3 to +0.3, moderate association ranges from -0.5 to -0.3 or 0.3 to 0.5, strong association ranges from -0.9 to -0.5 or 0.5 to 0.9 and very strong correlation ranges from -1.0 to -0.9 or 0.9 to 1.0 respectively.

Table 6: Summary result of hypothesis 2

		Economic benefits	Tourism activities
Economic benefits	Pearson		
	Correlation	1	.612
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.197
	N	6	6
Tourism activities	Pearson		
	Correlation	.612	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.197	
	N	6	6

The activities that are greatly influenced by tourism are presented in figure 1 in a bar chart. The bar chart also shows that sports competitions and traditional dance are the major tourism activities that greatly influence rural country development in the area.

Figure 1: A bar chart showing tourism activities that greatly influence economic growth and development in the study areas

Source: Field survey (2018)

The challenges of pro-poor tourism in the area

The challenges of pro-poor tourism in the area printed in table shows that lack of effective tourism framework and poor leadership were the major challenges to effective operationalization of pro-poor tourism in the area with values of 37.50 percent and 21.25

percent followed by communities' poor attitude to tourism with a value of 19.50 percent. Table 5 indicate that lack of awareness and poor government policies were also challenges to pro-poor tourism in the area as observed with values of 10 percent and 7.75 percent.

Figure 2: The challenges of pro-poor tourism in the area

Source: Field survey (2018)

Conclusion

Pro-poor tourism is an aspect of tourism which generally focuses on the wellbeing of citizens especially within rural communities. The research used tourism activities to effectively operationalize the concept of Pro-poor tourism with respect to infrastructural development in two Local Government Areas of Cross River State. The research findings revealed that tourism activities have significantly enhanced the economic wellbeing of the people as observed in the communication enhancement, increase in business activities, and increase in road network among others. Besides, the research finding has also proved that various tourism activities give rise to the various development and infrastructural development in the area. This development has impacted positively on the study area.

However, in spite of the tremendous impact of tourism activities which is a component used in operationalizing pro-poor tourism, pro-poor tourism is not devoid of challenges, ranging from poor governance, poor leadership style among others in the area. It is on this premise that effective mechanism is needed to ensure smooth operationalization of the concept of pro-poor tourism with respect of infrastructural development and economic benefits in the area.

Recommendations

The operationalization of pro-poor concept using tourism activities is not devoid of challenges in the study area. Therefore, the following recommendations are hereby put forward to avert the challenges that are associated with pro-poor tourism in the area.

1. Government should develop a tourism framework that would ensure tourism related activities all year round. This would help to encourage increase in business activities, income generation among others hence improving the standard of living of the people. Beside, these activities would help in periodic maintenance and provision of rural social amenities that would better the wellbeing of the people.
2. Government at all level should develop sound tourism policies that would drive tourism and encourage full participation of the local people in tourism activities in the area.
3. Government should periodically organize an enlightenment campaign. This would help create public and rural awareness towards the benefits accrue towards the development of tourism activities in the area.
4. The various stakeholders in the tourism industry should initiate programmes that would enhance community development especially as regards to the provision of social infrastructure. This social infrastructure will encourage tourists from all angles in the world to the study area.

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